

Analyzing Generative AI Adoption Across Generational Groups in Higher Education Using NLP and Machine Learning

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Abstract—Generative artificial intelligence (GenAI) has become widely used in higher education, yet adoption studies rarely combine generational comparison with natural language processing (NLP) and machine learning (ML). This study examined GenAI adoption across Generation Z ($n = 150$), Millennials ($n = 96$), and Generation X ($n = 26$) in five higher education institutions in Phnom Penh, Cambodia ($N = 272$). A quantitative cross-sectional survey measured Perceived Usefulness (PU), Perceived Ease of Use (PEOU), Trust and Ethical Concerns (TEC), and Acceptance and Intention to Use (ATU), together with open-ended responses. The analysis applied descriptive statistics, one-way ANOVA, Tukey HSD, TF-IDF feature extraction, and supervised classification using Logistic Regression, Support Vector Machine (SVM), and Random Forest. Results showed that 256 respondents (94.1%) had used GenAI for academic purposes. Only PEOU showed a statistically significant generational difference, $F(2,269) = 3.8435$, $p = .0226$, with Tukey HSD indicating that Generation Z rated GenAI easier to use than Millennials ($p = .0176$). TF-IDF results showed that respondents emphasized research, help, ideas, information, benefits, and limitations. For acceptance classification, Logistic Regression achieved the best cross-validation macro-F1 (0.7147), while SVM achieved the highest held-out test macro-F1 (0.8220). For generational classification, Logistic Regression was the best cross-validation model (macro-F1 = 0.5184), showing that generational language patterns exist but remain difficult to classify because Generation X was underrepresented. The findings suggest that institutions should provide ease-of-use support, clear responsible-use guidelines, and balanced AI literacy training across cohorts.

Index Terms—Generative AI, higher education, Technology Acceptance Model, generational differences, NLP, TF-IDF, machine learning, Cambodia.

I. INTRODUCTION

Generative artificial intelligence (GenAI) tools such as ChatGPT, Grammarly, QuillBot, and Google Translate are increasingly used in higher education for writing support, concept explanation, research assistance, translation, and idea generation [1], [2], [3]. Recent reports show rapid growth in student AI use, while faculty adoption and institutional policy development remain uneven [4], [5]. This makes GenAI adoption an important issue for universities that must balance productivity, learning support, academic integrity, and responsible use.

Generational differences are especially relevant because students and educators often develop digital habits in different technological periods. Recent studies suggest that Generation Z students are more interested in adopting GenAI than older Millennial and Generation X educators, while older cohorts may raise more concerns about academic integrity, reliability, and critical thinking [6], [7], [8]. However, many studies still rely mainly on structured Likert-scale surveys and do not fully analyze open-ended feedback. This limits understanding of how respondents describe GenAI in their own words.

This study addresses that gap by combining survey-based Technology Acceptance Model (TAM) constructs with NLP and ML. The research is organized around four questions: (1) What usage behaviors and adoption patterns appear across Generation Z, Millennials, and Generation X? (2) What linguistic patterns emerge from open-ended feedback? (3) Which textual features contribute to predicting GenAI acceptance? (4) How do Logistic Regression, SVM, and Random Forest compare in acceptance prediction and generational classification?

II. RELATED WORK

TAM explains technology adoption through PU and PEOU, which influence user attitude and intention to use a system [9]. Recent GenAI education studies show that PU, ease of use, trust, and behavioral intention remain important predictors of adoption, while plagiarism, reliability, and responsible-use concerns extend the original TAM framework [10], [11], [12], [13]. Therefore, this study uses PU, PEOU, TEC, and ATU as the main survey constructs.

Generational Cohort Theory argues that people who grow up during similar historical and technological conditions may develop shared behavioral tendencies [14]. Recent higher education studies provide updated support for this view by showing that generational background can shape AI comfort, adoption intention, and perceptions of risk [6], [7], [8]. In this study, Generation Z, Millennials, and Generation X are compared to examine whether these cohort differences appear in GenAI usage, TAM construct scores, and open-ended language.

NLP allows open-ended text to be transformed into analyzable numerical data. TF-IDF remains a standard feature extraction method because it weights terms by frequency and uniqueness within a corpus [15], [16]. Recent educational research shows that NLP can extract meaningful patterns from open-ended survey responses, stakeholder sentiment, and learner feedback [17], [18], [19], [20], [21]. Logistic Regression, SVM, and Random Forest are common supervised classifiers for text classification because they provide different strengths: interpretability, high-dimensional text separation, and non-linear ensemble learning [22], [23], [24]. A recent AI-adoption study also shows that classical ML and transformer-based models can be applied to higher education AI sentiment analysis [25].

III. METHODOLOGY

A. Research Design and Participants

This study used a quantitative cross-sectional design. Data were collected from five higher education institutions in Phnom Penh, Cambodia: Paragon International University, National School of Planning and Statistics, Western University, National Institute of Agriculture, and CAMED Business School. Respondents were grouped by birth year into Generation Z (1997–2012), Millennials (1981–1996), and Generation X (1965–1980). After cleaning, the final dataset contained 272 valid responses: Generation Z ($n = 150$, 55.1%), Millennials ($n = 96$, 35.3%), and Generation X ($n = 26$, 9.6%).

B. Survey Instrument and Measures

The survey included demographic items, GenAI usage questions, 5-point Likert-scale construct items, and three open-ended questions. The constructs were PU, PEOU, TEC, and ATU. Acceptance labels were derived from ATU mean scores using the Likert interpretation scale: Positive for $ATU \geq 3.41$, Neutral for 2.61–3.40, and Negative for $ATU < 2.61$. This produced Positive ($n = 145$, 53.3%), Neutral ($n = 83$, 30.5%), and Negative ($n = 44$, 16.2%) classes.

C. NLP and Feature Engineering

Open-ended responses were concatenated per respondent and preprocessed using NLTK. The steps included lowercasing, punctuation removal, tokenization, stopword removal, and lemmatization. The average number of tokens decreased from 55.8 before preprocessing to 30.7 after preprocessing, and three responses became empty after cleaning. TF-IDF vectorization was then applied with unigram and bigram features. For ML, the final feature matrix contained 500 TF-IDF features plus three non-target Likert predictors (PU, PEOU, and TEC), giving 503 combined features; ATU was used to derive the acceptance label. An 80/20 stratified split was used, producing 217 training samples and 55 held-out test samples.

TF-IDF was computed as:

$$TF(t, d) = \frac{\text{count of term } t \text{ in document } d}{\text{total terms in document } d} \quad (1)$$

$$IDF(t, D) = \log\left(\frac{N}{df_t}\right), \quad (2)$$

$$TFIDF(t, d) = TF(t, d) \times IDF(t, D).$$

D. Statistical and ML Analysis

One-way ANOVA tested generational differences in PU, PEOU, TEC, and ATU at $\alpha = .05$. When ANOVA was significant, Tukey HSD identified the specific group difference. Three supervised classifiers were compared: Logistic Regression, SVM with RBF kernel, and Random Forest. Five-fold stratified cross-validation was used for model comparison, and final evaluation was performed on the held-out test set. Macro-F1 was emphasized because both acceptance labels and generational groups were imbalanced.

IV. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

A. Respondent Profile and Usage Patterns

The sample was dominated by Generation Z, followed by Millennials and Generation X. Overall, 256 respondents (94.1%) reported using GenAI for academic purposes, while 16 respondents (5.9%) had not used it. Generation Z reported the highest use rate (98.7%), followed by Millennials (89.6%) and Generation X (84.6%) (Fig. 1).

Fig. 1: Respondent distribution by generation and acceptance label distribution ($N = 272$).

The most common frequency category was Sometimes ($n = 122$, 45.0%), followed by Often ($n = 79$, 29.2%) and Very Often ($n = 36$, 13.3%). Generation Z had the highest Very Often share (20.1%), while Millennials were mostly concentrated in Sometimes use (56.2%). Generation X showed a high Often share (42.3%), but its small sample size should be interpreted carefully (Fig. 2).

Fig. 2: Frequency of GenAI use by generation.

B. TAM Construct Scores and ANOVA

Table I shows that all groups reported moderate to positive construct scores. PEOU was the only statistically significant construct, $F(2,269) = 3.8435$, $p = .0226$. Tukey HSD showed that Generation Z scored significantly higher than Millennials on PEOU (mean difference = 0.328, $p = .0176$). PU, TEC, and ATU were not statistically different across generations (Table I; Fig. 3).

TABLE I: TAM Construct Scores and ANOVA Results by Generation

Construct	Gen Z M(SD)	Mill. M(SD)	Gen X M(SD)	F	p
PU	3.64(1.04)	3.40(0.90)	3.69(1.06)	1.9698	.1415
PEOU	3.57(0.98)	3.24(0.78)	3.51(0.94)	3.8435	.0226*
TEC	3.45(0.96)	3.35(0.73)	3.36(0.72)	0.4130	.6621
ATU	3.59(1.05)	3.36(0.90)	3.42(1.06)	1.5569	.2127

* $p < .05$. Mill. = Millennials; TEC = Trust and Ethical Concerns.

Fig. 3: Mean TAM construct scores by generational group.

C. Linguistic Patterns from Open-Ended Feedback

TF-IDF analysis showed that respondents most often discussed GenAI in relation to use, research, help, ideas, answers, information, study, benefits, ease of use, and understanding (Fig. 4). To make the generational language patterns clearer, Table II summarizes the most distinctive terms for each group. Generation Z emphasized academic-task support, Millennials emphasized practical evaluation and information use, and Generation X emphasized usefulness, speed, convenience, and limitations.

Fig. 4: Overall top TF-IDF terms in open-ended feedback.

TABLE II: Distinctive TF-IDF Terms by Generational Group

Generation	Distinctive feedback terms	Main pattern
Gen Z	good; assignment; lesson; academic; summarize; generate; idea; learn	Learning and academic-task support
Millennials	provide; document; comment; disadvantage; information; knowledge; answer; benefit	Practical evaluation, information use, and concerns
Gen X	useful; never; limit; fast; benefit; convenient; allow; study research; exam	Usefulness, speed, convenience, and limitations

D. Textual Features Predicting GenAI Acceptance

This part focuses on feedback-based predictors of GenAI acceptance. Therefore, Table III reports only TF-IDF words and phrases extracted from open-ended responses; Likert construct variables are not listed in the table. Logistic Regression coefficients were used for interpretation because they indicate which textual features pushed the model toward Negative, Neutral, or Positive acceptance. Positive acceptance was linked to academic support and productive-use terms such as analyze data, brainstorm idea, text, and lesson. Neutral acceptance was linked to balanced or conditional use, including summarize, moderate, information, easy, and source. Negative acceptance was linked to dependence, quality, and responsible-use concerns, including make people, without, standard, boundary, and never.

TABLE III: Textual Feedback Features Predicting Acceptance

Class	Feedback terms	Interpretation
Negative	make people; fast; analysis; write; without; standard; boundary; never	Concern about dependence, quality, and usage limits
Neutral	summarize; level; user; moderate; learn; information; easy; source	Balanced, cautious, or conditional use
Positive	yes; analyze data; brainstorm idea; analyze; text; lesson; sure	Academic support, productivity, and confidence in use

E. Machine Learning Model Comparison

Table IV presents the model comparison. For GenAI acceptance classification, Logistic Regression achieved the best cross-validation macro-F1 (0.7147), while SVM had the highest held-out test macro-F1 (0.8220). Because cross-validation is more stable across folds, Logistic Regression was selected as the best CV model for Task A. For generational classification, Logistic Regression clearly achieved the best cross-validation macro-F1 (0.5184), outperforming Random Forest and SVM.

TABLE IV: ML Model Performance Comparison

Task	Model	CV Macro-F1	Test Macro-F1
Acceptance	Logistic Regression	0.7147 ± 0.0698	0.7526
Acceptance	SVM (RBF)	0.6997 ± 0.0816	0.8220
Acceptance	Random Forest	0.6492 ± 0.0552	0.8111
Generation	Logistic Regression	0.5184 ± 0.0524	0.4848
Generation	SVM (RBF)	0.3465 ± 0.0734	0.3217
Generation	Random Forest	0.4201 ± 0.0285	0.3810

Hypothesis testing showed that H1 was partially supported because only PEOU differed significantly across generations. H2 was partially supported: ANOVA on five-fold CV macro-F1 scores showed significant model variation for Task B, $F = 9.9791$, $p = .0028$, with Tukey HSD indicating that Logistic Regression significantly outperformed SVM ($p = .0021$). For

Task A, model variation was not statistically significant, $F = 0.9707$, $p = .4067$.

V. CONCLUSION

This study found that GenAI adoption is common among higher education respondents in Phnom Penh, Cambodia, with 94.1% reporting academic use. Generational differences were visible in usage behavior and perceived ease of use, but not across all TAM constructs. Generation Z found GenAI significantly easier to use than Millennials, suggesting that ease-of-use training may be especially useful for cohorts with lower PEOU scores.

Open-ended feedback showed that respondents described GenAI mainly as a tool for research, help, information, ideas, and academic support, while also mentioning limitations and responsible-use concerns. ML results showed that acceptance classification was more successful than generational classification. Logistic Regression was the most reliable cross-validation model for both tasks, although SVM produced the highest held-out test F1 for acceptance classification. The weaker generational classification results indicate that larger and more balanced samples, especially for Generation X, are needed in future work.

ETHICS STATEMENT

Ethical review and approval were waived by the Faculty of Information and Computer Technology, Paragon International University, as the study involved anonymous, voluntary, minimal-risk survey responses and did not collect personally identifying information. Informed consent was obtained from all participants before they proceeded with the online survey.

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CONFLICTS OF INTEREST

The authors declare no conflicts of interest.

DATA AVAILABILITY

The anonymized dataset and Jupyter Notebook analysis code are available from the corresponding author upon reasonable request.

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